

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY AND SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY MEDIATED BY CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT KAFE KUDU, JALAN SEI PETANI, MEDAN CITY

Najmus Tsaqib*¹, Iskandarini,² Beby Karina Fawzee Sembiring³

^{1,2,3}Master of Management Program, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

Received : 01 October 2025
Revised : 10 October 2025
Accepted : 15 November 2025

Published : 23 December 2025
DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/morfai.v6i1.4726>
Publish Link : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/MORFAI/article/view/4726>

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of product quality and service quality on customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable at Kafe Kudu, Jalan Sei Petani, Medan City. The approach used is quantitative with the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method. The sample consisted of 90 respondents selected through purposive sampling. The results show that product quality does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction but has a significant influence on customer loyalty. Conversely, service quality has a significant impact on both customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Furthermore, customer satisfaction significantly affects customer loyalty. Mediation testing indicates that customer satisfaction does not significantly mediate the relationship between product quality and loyalty but does significantly mediate the relationship between service quality and customer loyalty. These findings suggest that, in the context of Kafe Kudu, improving service quality is a more effective strategy for building customer satisfaction and loyalty than focusing solely on product quality. Therefore, management is advised to prioritize enhancing service quality as a long-term strategic effort.

Keywords: *Cafe; Customer Loyalty; Customer Satisfaction; Product Quality; Service Quality*

1. INTRODUCTION

The culinary industry, particularly cafés, has experienced rapid growth in line with changes in urban lifestyles. Cafés today are not only places to eat, but also serve as social spaces and lifestyle hubs that offer unique experiences to customers (Febriatu Sholikhah & Hadita, 2023). Amid increasingly intense competition, maintaining customer loyalty has become a major challenge for business actors, including Kafe Kudu located on Jalan Sei Petani, Medan City. Customer loyalty is influenced by various factors, including product quality and service quality (Kristy Manihuruk, 2023). Good product quality reflects the alignment between customer expectations and the reality received, such as taste, presentation, and menu consistency (Dianta Purba et al., 2025). Meanwhile, service quality includes interpersonal aspects, service speed, and the comfort experienced by customers during their visit to the café.

However, loyalty is not always formed directly—it can be mediated by the level of customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction reflects an overall evaluation of the consumer experience which, if positive, increases their tendency to return and recommend the café to others (Wasistho & Toto Rahardjo, 2023). Several previous studies have shown varying results regarding the relationships among these variables. Therefore, it is essential to re-examine empirically whether product quality and service quality have a direct impact on customer loyalty, as well as the extent to which customer satisfaction acts as a mediating variable in the context of Kafe Kudu. This study aims to analyze the influence of product quality and service quality on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction, using a quantitative approach and the Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method. The results of this study are expected to provide both theoretical and practical contributions to efforts in enhancing customer loyalty in the café sector.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the theoretical review, the hypotheses in this study are formulated as presented in the conceptual framework (Figure 1) as follows:

- H1: Product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.
- H2: Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.
- H3: Product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.
- H4: Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

H5: Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

H6: Product quality has an indirect effect on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

H7: Service quality has an indirect effect on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
 Source: Processed Data (2025).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Product Quality

Product quality is a key aspect in meeting consumer needs and satisfaction. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012), quality reflects the product's ability to perform its functions, such as durability, reliability, ease of use, and conformity with consumer expectations. (Tjiptono, 2020) adds that product quality encompasses everything that provides value in meeting consumers' needs and desires—not only in terms of function but also perceived benefits. Thus, product quality is a characteristic designed by companies to meet customer expectations, enhance satisfaction, and strengthen competitiveness.

Food (Product) Quality Indicators

According to (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2020) in their book *Service, Quality and Satisfaction*, food quality is influenced by several key factors that determine customer satisfaction with the food served. These factors include color, appearance, portion or standard portion size, shape, temperature, texture, and aroma. Collectively, these seven aspects contribute to consumers' perception of the food quality, in terms of visual appeal, taste, and overall sensory experience.

Service Quality

According to (Kotler & Keller, 2016b), service quality should focus on customer needs and be measured from the customer's perception, not from the service provider's perspective. The perception of quality is determined by how customers experience and assess the service provided. High-quality service includes both direct and indirect interactions between customers and providers, aiming to effectively resolve customer issues. In industries where physical product differentiation is minimal, added service value—such as ease of ordering, delivery, training, and after-sales service—becomes a key differentiator in enhancing customer satisfaction.

Service Quality Indicators

According to (Tjiptono, 2019) service quality can be measured through five main dimensions commonly used to assess customer experience. These dimensions include: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. These five dimensions reflect important aspects of the service process—from the provider's ability to deliver on promises, speed and responsiveness in meeting customer needs, to personal attitude and physical facilities that support optimal service delivery.

Customer Satisfaction

According to (Kristianto, 2011), customer satisfaction arises from the comparison between product expectations and the actual experience after use. If the result meets or exceeds expectations, the buyer will feel satisfied; if not, disappointment will occur. Satisfaction is also an emotional reaction to the perceived benefits relative to the sacrifices made. The greater the perceived relative benefit, the higher the satisfaction level. (Kotler & Keller, 2016c) further state that customer satisfaction greatly influences loyalty and future purchasing decisions, with expectations usually shaped by personal experience, recommendations, and advertising.

Customer Satisfaction Indicators

According to (Kotler & Keller, 2016a) there are five key indicators that influence customer satisfaction levels: product quality, service quality, emotional factors, price, and additional costs. Customers feel satisfied when the product received has good quality and the service provided meets expectations. Moreover, emotional factors such as pride or social status gained from using the product also influence satisfaction. Competitive pricing and minimal additional costs or time required to obtain the product further enhance overall satisfaction.

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty is a customer's commitment to a brand, store, or service provider, developed through repeated positive experiences and minimal complaints. It arises from consistent satisfaction with the company's performance in delivering services and solving problems. According to (Tjiptono, 2016), loyalty is also reflected in consistent repeat purchases and the customer's willingness to recommend the product or service to others.

Customer Loyalty Indicators

According to (Alma, 2018), customer loyalty is demonstrated through purchasing behavior that is based on awareness and careful consideration in decision-making. A loyal customer not only makes regular repeat purchases but is also likely to recommend the product or service to others. Additionally, loyal customers show resistance to competitive offers, meaning they continue to choose the same product or service despite the availability of other alternatives. These three indicators reflect loyalty built on sustained satisfaction and trust in the brand.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach with the aim of testing the relationships between variables in the research model, which includes Product Quality (X1), Service Quality (X2), Customer Satisfaction (Y), and Customer Loyalty (Z). This approach was chosen to obtain a systematic and measurable overview of the direct and indirect effects among these variables. The population in this study consists of customers who have visited and made at least one purchase within the last month at Kafe Kudu, located on Jalan Sei Petani, Medan City. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, which involves selecting respondents who are deemed relevant to the research objectives (Imansari & Klolifah, 2023). A total of 90 respondents were selected, all of whom met the criteria as active customers (Slolihin & Ratnomo, 2021).

The research instrument is a questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" (1) to "Strongly Agree" (5). The questionnaire consists of several indicators formulated based on previous relevant theories for each variable. (Hafni Sahir, 2021) The data analysis technique used is Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), processed using SmartPLS 4.0 software. This tool was chosen due to its ability to test relationships between latent variables with relatively small sample sizes and to examine both the structural model and measurement model simultaneously. Validity and reliability tests were first conducted to ensure that the research instruments were appropriate for use. Subsequently, path analysis was performed to determine the direct and indirect effects among variables. Significance testing was based on a T-statistic value > 1.96 and a P-value < 0.05 , as recommended by (Hair et al., 2021).

Model Evaluation Analysis

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Validity

Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity (Outer Loading)

Convergent validity testing was conducted through the outer loading value for each indicator (Audria Deva Ananda & Achmad, 2025). The analysis results show that all indicators of Product Quality (X1), Service Quality

(X2), Customer Satisfaction (Y), and Customer Loyalty (Z) have outer loading values above 0.7. This indicates that all indicators are valid and consistently represent their respective constructs. This finding aligns with the criteria stated by (Hamid & Anwar, 2019) which indicate that an outer loading value of ≥ 0.7 demonstrates good indicator validity.

Convergent Validity (Average Variance Extracted - AVE)

Each construct in the model meets the convergent validity criteria, as indicated by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values exceeding the minimum threshold of 0.50. This suggests that the proportion of variance explained by the indicators in relation to the construct is greater than the variance caused by measurement error. Thus, all constructs in this study are declared convergently valid in accordance with the guidelines of (Arifin et al., 2023).

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Discriminant validity testing using the Fornell-Larcker approach shows that all constructs have square root values of AVE higher than their correlation with other constructs. For instance, Product Quality (0.790) is higher than its correlation with Customer Satisfaction (0.644), Service Quality (0.732), and Loyalty (0.506). The same applies to other constructs. This result meets the criteria of (Haryono, 2016) which state that discriminant validity is achieved if the square root of AVE exceeds inter-construct correlations. Therefore, all constructs in this model demonstrate good discriminant validity and can be clearly distinguished from one another.

Discriminant Validity (Cross Loading)

Testing discriminant validity using the cross-loading method shows that all indicators have the highest loading on their respective constructs compared to other constructs (Salim et al., 2022). For example, indicator X1.1 has a loading value of 0.824 on Product Quality, which is higher than its correlation with other constructs. This finding is in line with the criteria of (Haryono, 2016), which state that discriminant validity is achieved if an indicator more strongly represents its intended construct than any other. Therefore, all indicators in this model are declared valid and capable of accurately measuring their constructs.

Discriminant Validity (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations - HTMT)

Discriminant validity testing through the HTMT approach indicates that all inter-construct values are below the threshold of 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015). The highest HTMT value is 0.873 between Satisfaction and Loyalty, while others range from 0.564 to 0.832. All these values fall within acceptable limits, indicating that each construct is distinct and does not overlap (Lukman et al., 2024). Thus, discriminant validity in this model is well established.

Reliability

All constructs in this research model are proven to be reliable, as evidenced by Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values exceeding the threshold of 0.70. These values indicate that the indicators for each latent variable—product quality, service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty—have high internal consistency. Therefore, the measurement tools used in this study meet reliability criteria and are deemed trustworthy for further analysis, in line with the criteria outlined by (Haryono, 2016).

Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

The inner model evaluation aims to assess the relationships between latent constructs, both directly and indirectly. This analysis also includes testing the coefficient of determination (R^2), effect size (f^2), and predictive relevance (Q^2) to ensure the empirical strength and accuracy of the model.

Path Coefficient (Direct Effects)

The results of direct effect testing presented in Figure 2 and Table 1 show that most paths in this research model have significant directional effects. First, the relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction ($X1 \rightarrow Y$) is positive, with a coefficient of 0.169; however, the effect is not statistically significant, with a T-statistic of 1.677 and a P-value of 0.094, exceeding the 0.05 significance threshold. Second, the path from product quality to customer loyalty ($X1 \rightarrow Z$) shows a negative direction with a coefficient of -0.185, yet is statistically significant, with a T-statistic of 2.304 and a P-value of 0.021. Hence, although the direction is negative, the effect remains statistically significant.

Next, the path from service quality to customer satisfaction ($X2 \rightarrow Y$) shows a strong positive and significant effect, with a coefficient of 0.648, a T-statistic of 6.438, and a P-value of 0.000, indicating that service quality is a primary driver of customer satisfaction. The path from service quality to customer loyalty ($X2 \rightarrow Z$) also shows a positive and significant effect, with a coefficient of 0.435, a T-statistic of 3.567, and a P-value of 0.000. Lastly, the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty ($Y \rightarrow Z$) is also positive and significant, with a coefficient of 0.579, a T-statistic of 5.391, and a P-value of 0.000. Thus, of the six direct relationship paths tested, five exhibit significant positive effects, except for one path from product quality to customer satisfaction, which is not significant, and one path from product quality to customer loyalty, which is significant but negatively directed.

Figure 2. Path Coefficient Results (Direct Effects)
 Source: Processed data using SmartPLS (2025).

According to (Hair et al., 2021), the relationship between variables is considered significant if the *t-statistic* value is greater than 1.96 and the *p-value* is less than 0.05 at a 5% significance level. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that only the influence of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction is not significant in this model. Meanwhile, Service Quality has a significant effect on the other two variables, and Customer Satisfaction also plays a crucial role in shaping Customer Loyalty.

Table 1. Path Coefficient Results / Direct Relationships

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Hair et al. (2021) T statistics (O/STDEV)	Hair et al. (2021) P values	Description
				1.96	> 0.05	< =
				Significant	Significant	
(X1) Product Quality → (Y) Customer Satisfaction	0,169	0,179	0,101	1,677	0,094	Positive and Not Significant
(X1) Product Quality → (Z) Customer Loyalty	-0,185	-0,195	0,080	2,304	0,021	Negative and Significant
(X2) Service Quality → (Y) Customer Satisfaction	0,648	0,644	0,101	6,438	0,000	Positive and Significant
(X2) Service Quality → (Z) Customer Loyalty	0,435	0,444	0,122	3,567	0,000	Positive and Significant
(Y) Customer Satisfaction → (Z) Customer Loyalty	0,579	0,582	0,107	5,391	0,000	Positive and Significant

Indirect Effect (Specific Indirect Effect)

Based on Table 2, the indirect effect of product quality (X1) on customer loyalty (Z) through customer satisfaction (Y) shows a positive coefficient of 0.098; however, it is not statistically significant, with a T-statistic of 1.514 and a P-value of 0.130. This indicates that although the direction of the relationship is positive, customer satisfaction does not serve as a significant mediator in bridging the effect of product quality on customer loyalty. Conversely, the indirect effect of service quality (X2) on customer loyalty (Z) through customer satisfaction (Y) displays a positive coefficient of 0.375 and is statistically significant, with a T-statistic of 4.517 and a P-value of 0.000. These findings indicate that customer satisfaction effectively mediates the relationship between service quality and customer loyalty. Therefore, only the path X2 → Y → Z meets the significance criteria as outlined by (Hair et al., 2021), namely T-statistic > 1.96 and P-value < 0.05, while the path X1 → Y → Z does not fulfill these conditions. According to the criteria of (Hair et al., 2021), an indirect effect is considered statistically significant if the T-statistic > 1.96 and the P-value < 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that in this model, only the mediation path from Service Quality to Loyalty through Satisfaction is statistically significant.

Table 2. Specific Indirect Effect Results / Indirect Relationship

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Hair et al. (2021) statistics (O/STDEV)	Hair et al. (2021) T values	Description P < = Significant
(X1) Product Quality → (Y) Customer Satisfaction → (Z) Loyalty	0,098	0,105	0,065	1,514	0,130	Positive and Not Significant
(X2) Service Quality → (Y) Customer Satisfaction → (Z) Loyalty	0,375	0,372	0,083	4,517	0,000	Positive and Significant

Model Quality Evaluation

R-square (R²)

The results in Table 3 show that the Satisfaction variable has an R² value of 0.609, while Loyalty has an R² value of 0.691. This means that 60.9% of the variance in Satisfaction is explained by Product Quality and Service Quality, whereas 69.1% of the variance in Loyalty is explained by all three variables in the model. Referring to (Hamid & Anwar, 2019) and (Aditiya Kesuma, 2022), an R² value between 0.50 and 0.75 is categorized as moderate. Therefore, this model demonstrates good predictive ability, especially in explaining Loyalty as the main dependent variable.

Table 3. Value R-square

	R-square
(Y) Customer Satisfaction	0,609
(Z) Customer Loyalty	0,691

f-square (f²)

The results in Table 4 indicate that Product Quality (X1) has a small effect on Satisfaction (f² = 0.034) and Loyalty (f² = 0.050). In contrast, Service Quality (X2) has a large effect on Satisfaction (f² = 0.497) and a medium effect on Loyalty (f² = 0.190). Meanwhile, Customer Satisfaction (Y) has a large effect on Loyalty (f² = 0.425). Referring to (Savitri et al., 2021) and (Arifin et al., 2023), an f² value greater than 0.35 is categorized as large, between 0.02–0.15 as medium, and less than 0.02 as small. Therefore, Service Quality and Satisfaction are the dominant contributors influencing Customer Loyalty in this model.

Table 4. Value f-square

	(X1) Product Quality	(X2) Service Quality	(Y) Customer Satisfaction	(Z) Customer Loyalty
(X1) Product Quality			0,034	0,050
(X2) Service Quality			0,497	0,190
(Y) Customer Satisfaction				0,425
(Z) Customer Loyalty				

Q-square (Q²)

Based on Table 5, the Q² value is 0.580 for Satisfaction and 0.539 for Loyalty, indicating that the model has good predictive relevance. These values suggest that the endogenous variables can be adequately predicted by the independent constructs. Referring to (Haryono, 2016), Q² is considered relevant if the value is greater than 0. Therefore, the model in this study demonstrates strong predictive quality and is appropriate for testing the relationships among variables.

Tabel 5. Value Q-square

	Q ² predict
(Y) Customer Satisfaction	0,580
(Z) Customer Loyalty	0,539

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study aims to analyze the effect of product quality and service quality on customer loyalty, with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable. Based on data processed using SmartPLS 4.0 from 90 respondents, the following results were obtained:

Effect of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction

The test results show that product quality does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This finding is indicated by a T-statistic value of 1.677 and a P-value of 0.094, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected. This suggests that customers' perceptions of product quality are not sufficient to directly generate satisfaction.

Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Service quality is proven to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. A T-statistic of 6.438 and a P-value of 0.000 indicate that the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted. Good, responsive, and friendly service has a strong impact on customers' feelings of satisfaction during their visit to Kafe Kudu.

Effect of Product Quality on Customer Loyalty

Product quality has a negative yet significant effect on customer loyalty, with a T-statistic value of 2.304 and a P-value of 0.021. The third hypothesis (H3) is accepted, although the negative direction indicates that perceptions of product quality may decrease loyalty. This may suggest unmet customer expectations or a stronger preference for other factors such as service and ambiance.

Effect of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty

Service quality also has a significant effect on customer loyalty, as indicated by a T-statistic value of 3.567 and a P-value of 0.000. Thus, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted. Customers who experience high-quality service tend to return and recommend the café to others.

Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on loyalty, as shown by a T-statistic of 5.391 and a P-value of 0.000. The fifth hypothesis (H5) is accepted. High satisfaction fosters a positive emotional relationship between the customer and the café, ultimately strengthening customer loyalty.

Mediating Role of Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction does not significantly mediate the relationship between product quality and customer loyalty (T-statistic = 1.514; P-value = 0.130), so the sixth hypothesis (H6) is rejected. However, customer satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of service quality on customer loyalty (T-statistic = 4.517; P-value = 0.000), thus the seventh hypothesis (H7) is accepted. This indicates that in the context of Kafe Kudu, good service quality not only creates satisfaction but also strengthens customer loyalty through a pleasant experience.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on data analysis from 90 respondents who are customers of Kafe Kudu on Jalan Sei Petani, Medan, this study yields several key conclusions. First, product quality does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction, indicating that a positive perception of the product is not sufficient to directly foster satisfaction. In contrast, service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, suggesting that service aspects play a dominant role in creating a positive customer experience. Second, product quality has a negative yet significant effect on customer loyalty, implying a potential mismatch between customer expectations and their perception of the product offered. On the other hand, service quality has a significant positive effect on loyalty, meaning that the better the service provided, the more likely customers are to remain loyal.

In addition, customer satisfaction significantly influences loyalty, indicating that satisfied customers are more likely to revisit and recommend Kafe Kudu to others. Lastly, customer satisfaction does not significantly mediate the relationship between product quality and loyalty, but it does significantly mediate the relationship between service quality and loyalty. This highlights that excellent service is the key driver in building customer loyalty at Kafe Kudu.

SUGGESTIONS

The management of Kafe Kudu is advised to prioritize improving service quality, such as staff friendliness, speed of service, and attentiveness to customer needs, as these aspects have been proven to significantly influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. Although product quality did not show a significant contribution to satisfaction, a comprehensive evaluation of the products remains essential—particularly regarding taste, presentation, and menu innovation—to meet customer expectations. Furthermore, long-term strategies should focus on integrating excellent service with the overall customer experience, including seating comfort, café ambiance, and emotional connections built with customers. For future research development, it is recommended to include additional variables such as emotional value, price perception, or brand image to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence customer loyalty in the culinary industry.

REFERENCES

- Aditya Kesuma, B. (2022). The influence of work motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Jambi Branch. *Jurnal Manajemen Terapan dan Keuangan (Mankeu)*, 11(1).
- Alma, B. (2018). *Marketing Management and Service Marketing* (Rev. ed.). Alfabeta.
- Arifin, M., Hikmah Perkasa, D., & Desty Febrian, W. (2023). *Global: Jurnal Lentera BITEP*. <https://lenteranusa.id/>
- Audria Deva Ananda, K., & Achmad, N. (2025). Employee retention as a mediator in the influence of talent management strategy on Generation Z performance in Solo Raya. *Paradoks: Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi*, 8(2).
- Dianta Purba, R., Fahriyal Aldi, M., & Herlambang, A. (2025). The influence of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in MSME Ompu Gende Coffee. *Jurnal Penelitian Nusantara*, 1, 44–48. <https://doi.org/10.59435/menulis.v1i1.18>
- Febriatu Sholikhah, A., & Hadita. (2023). The influence of service quality, product quality, and price on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction: A study on Mie Gacoan in East Bekasi. <http://report.licorice.pink/blog/mini-survey/indonesian-preference-than-anything->
- Hafni Sahir, S. (2021). *Research Methodology* (P. Kreatif & A. Rochmah, Eds.). KBM Indonesia Publisher.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Hamid, & Anwar. (2019). The influence of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in restaurant industries in Makassar City. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen dan Ekonomi Terapan*.
- Haryono, S. (2016). *SEM Methods for Management Research: AMOS, LISREL, PLS*. Luxima Metro Media.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Imansari, N., & Klolifah, U. (2023). *Research Methodology for Vocational Education*. UNIPMA Press, Universitas PGRI Madiun.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management* (14th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016a). *Marketing Management* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016b). *Marketing Management in Indonesia: Analysis, Planning, Implementation, and Control* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016c). *Marketing Management* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Kristianto, P. (2011). *Service Marketing Management*. Andi Offset.
- Kristy Manihuruk, B. (2023). Analysis of product quality and promotion on customer loyalty with satisfaction as an intervening variable at PT Shopee Indonesia. *Business Management*, 1(1). https://ejournal.uhn.ac.id/index.php/business_management
- Lukman, H., Mayasari, A., Muflihah, N., & Ayu Nuning, F. (2024). The effect of price, design, and quality on customer satisfaction in purchasing sports jerseys. *Jurnal Penelitian Bidang Inovasi & Pengelolaan Industri*, 3(2), 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.33752/invantri.v3i2.5602>

- Salim, F., Arif, S., & Devi, A. (2022). The influence of Islamic financial literacy, Islamic branding, and religiosity on student decisions in using Islamic banking services: A study on FAI students at Ibn Khaldun University Bogor (class of 2017–2018), 5, 226.
- Savitri, E., Sari, R. N., & Putra, Y. (2021). The effect of service quality and product quality on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediation variable. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 10(6), 34–40.
- Slolihin, M., & Ratnomo, D. (2021). *SEM-PLS Analysis using WarpPLS 7.0*. Clara Mitak.
- Tjiptono, F. (2016). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction* (Rev. ed.). Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F. (2019). *Service Management: Achieving Excellent Services* (2nd ed.). Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F. (2020). *Service Marketing: Principles, Implementation, and Research*. Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F., & Chandra, G. (2020). *Strategic Marketing* (3rd ed.). Andi Offset.
- Wasistho, A. S., & Toto Rahardjo, S. (2023). The influence of experiential marketing on customer loyalty through brand image and customer satisfaction: A study on 9 Typical Cafe Semarang customers. *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 12(4). <https://ejournal3.undip.ac.id/index.php/djom/index>
- Aditiya Kesuma, B. (2022). 32. jurnal tahun 2022 PENGARUH MOTIVASI KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA KARYAWAN MELALUI KEPUASAN KERJA SEBAGAI VARIABEL MEDIA PADA PT BANK TABUNGAN PENSIUNAN NASIONAL (BTPN) CABANG JAMBI. *Jurnal Manajemen Terapan Dan Keuangan (Mankeu)*, 11(01).
- Alma, B. (2018). *BibTeX a11 Manajemen Pemasaran dan Pemasaran Jasa* (Edisi Revisi). Alfabeta.
- Arifin, Magito, Hikmah Perkasa, D., & Desty Febrian, W. (2023). 29. jurnal tahun 2023 *Global : Jurnal Lentera BITEP*. <https://lenteranusa.id/>
- Audria Deva Ananda, K., & Achmad, N. (2025). 36. jurnal tahun 2025 Retensi Karyawan sebagai Mediasi dalam Pengaruh Strategi Manajemen Talenta terhadap Kinerja Generasi Z di Solo Raya. *PARADOKS Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi*, 8(2).
- Dianta Purba, R., Fahriyal Aldi, M., & Herlambang, A. (2025). 6. jurnal tahun 2025 Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Kepuasan Pelanggan Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan pada UMKM Ompu Gende Coffee. *Jurnal Penelitian Nusantara*, 1, 44–48. <https://doi.org/10.59435/menulis.v1i1.18>
- Febriatu Sholikhah, A., & Hadita. (2023). 1. jurnal tahun 2023 PENGARUH KUALITAS LAYANAN, KUALITAS PRODUK DAN HARGA TERHADAP LOYALITAS PELANGGAN MELALUI KEPUASAN PELANGGAN MIE GACOAN DI BEKASI TIMUR. <http://report.licorice.pink/blog/mini-survey/indonesian-preferrice-than-anything->
- Hafni Sahir, S. (2021). 1. buku tahun 2021 *Metodologi Penelitian* (P. Kreatif & A. Rochmah, Eds.). PENERBIT KBM INDONESIA .
- Hair, Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). *BibTeX a17 A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (3rd Edition). Sage Publications.
- Hamid, & Anwar. (2019). BibTeX a18 Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan dan Kepuasan Pelanggan terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan pada Industri Rumah Makan di Kota Makassar. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Dan Ekonomi Terapan*.
- Haryono, S. (2016). *BibTeX a16 Metode SEM untuk Penelitian Manajemen: AMOS, LISREL, PLS*. Luxima Metro Media.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). BibTeX a15 A New Criterion for Assessing Discriminant Validity in Variance-Based Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Imansari, N., & Klolifah, U. (2023). 3B tahun 2023 *METODOLOGI PENELITIAN UNTUK PENDIDIKAN KEJURUAN*. UNIPMA Press Universitas PGRI Madiun.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *BibTeX a1 Marketing Management* (14th Edition). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016a). *BibTeX a4 Marketing Management* (16th Edition). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016b). *BibTeX a8 Manajemen Pemasaran di Indonesia: Analisis, Perencanaan, Implementasi, dan Pengendalian* (16th Edition). Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016c). *BibTeX a9 Marketing Management* (16th Edition). Pearson Education.
- Kristianto, P. (2011). *BibTeX a7 Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa*. CV Andi Offset.
- Kristy Manihuruk, B. (2023). 2. jurnal tahun 2023 *ANALISIS KUALITAS PRODUK DAN PROMOSI TERHADAP LOYALITAS PELANGGAN DENGAN KEPUASAN SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING PADA PT SHOPEE INDONESIA* (Vol. 1, Issue 1). https://ejournal.uhn.ac.id/index.php/business_management

- Lukman, H., Mayasari, A., Muflihah, N., & Ayu Nuning, F. (2024). 33. jurnal tahun 2024 Pengaruh Harga, Desain, Dan Kualitas Kepada Kepuasan Pelanggan Dalam Membeli Jersey Olahraga. *Jurnal Penelitian Bidang Inovasi & Pengelolaan Industri*, 3(2), 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.33752/invantri.v3i2.5602>
- Salim, F., Arif, S., & Devi, A. (2022). 31. jurnal tahun 2022 Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan Syariah, Islamic Branding, dan Religiusitas terhadap Keputusan Mahasiswa Dalam Menggunakan Jasa Perbankan Syariah: Studi Pada Mahasiswa FAI Universitas Ibn Khaldun Bogor Angkatan 2017-2018. 5, 226.
- Savitri, E., Sari, R. N., & Putra, Y. (2021). BibTeX a19 The Effect of Service Quality and Product Quality on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction as a Mediation Variable. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 10(6), 34–40.
- Slolihin, M., & Ratnomo, D. (2021). 11b tahun 2021 Analisis SEM - PLS dengan WarpPLS 7.0 (Clara Mitak).
- Tjiptono, F. (2016). *BibTeX a10 Service, Quality & Satisfaction* (Edisi Revisi). Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F. (2019). *BibTeX a5 Service Management: Mewujudkan Layanan Prima* (Edisi 2). Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F. (2020). *BibTeX a2 Pemasaran Jasa: Prinsip, Penerapan, dan Penelitian*. Andi Offset.
- Tjiptono, F., & Chandra, G. (2020). *BibTeX a3 Pemasaran Strategik* (Edisi 3). Andi Offset.
- Wasistho, A. S., & Toto Rahardjo, S. (2023). 7. jurnal tahun 2023 Analisis Pengaruh Experiential Marketing terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Melalui Brand Image dan Customer Satisfaction (Studi pada Pelanggan 9 Typical Cafe Semarang). *DIPONEGORO JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT*, 12(4). <https://ejournal3.undip.ac.id/index.php/djom/index>